

Improving anything's ecological footprint using AI.

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Abstract. This paper presents a method to reduce most, if not all, human activities' footprint with a simple, consistent, and yet counter-intuitive use of AI. Our method is backed up by numerous scientific studies [1–9] and has proved to be efficient and easy to put into practice.

Just refrain from using AI.

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